

OVERVIEW TO THE IMPORTANCE OF SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS EXPRESSING MENTAL STATE

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Abstract: In speech communication, humans are not always in the same mental state. Therefore, words and phraseological units expressing mental state are also different. There are words and phraseological unit expressing positive and negative state as well. In this article some information about the meaning of phraseological units expressing mental state in Uzbek and English Languages(in the example of American culture) will be given.

Key words: Idioms, Mental state, phrase, compliment, emotion, feeling

Abstrakt: Inson nutqiy muloqot jarayonida doim ham bir xil ruhiy holatda bo'lavermaydi. Shunday ekan ruhiy holatni ifodalovchi so'zlar va frazeologik birliklar ham turlicha. Ijobiy ruhiy holatni ifodalovchi so'z va frazeologik birliklar bilan birga salbiylari ham bor. Bu maqolada O'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi (Amerika madaniyati misolida) ruhiy holarni ifodalovchi frazeologik birliklar ma'nolari haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: idioma, ruhiy holat, fraza, xushomad, his-tuyg'u, hissiyot.

An idiom is a phrase or phrase expressing a figurative, non-literal meaning, usually attached to an expression; but some idioms turn into idioms, keeping the literal meaning of the idiom. The figurative meaning of an idiom belonging to the group of formulaic languages differs from its literal meaning. Idioms are common in all languages; There are about twenty-five million idiomatic expressions in English alone.

A compliment is a nice thing you say to someone else about them. You can compliment someone on their appearance (clothing, smile, eyes, etc.), their work (writing, art, etc.), or even their qualities that you admire. Giving someone makes you feel good, and so does receiving compliments.

Emotions and feelings can be both positive and negative. Every day we experience one feeling or another, and sometimes there are such happy or exciting days that we are simply filled with positive emotions.

These feelings and emotions, positive or not, keep us alive, so let's learn to talk about them in English and share our joys and sorrows with our loved ones and friends railway.

Although positive expressions are used in all cultures, they are especially important for Uzbek and English cultures. Here are a few examples of their frequent use:

Playing sports. Uzbeks and Americans love sports. The most popular team sports are baseball, football, basketball, soccer and hockey. Positive expressions are important in playing sports. Coaches and teammates can help each other play better with words of encouragement

It's working. Americans are a hardworking bunch of people. CNN Money ranked the United States as the 7th hardest working country in the world. Being positive helps make hard work easy and enjoyable. Americans are also very optimistic (hopeful), if you are interested, you can read in this article.

Training. Whether you are a teacher or a student, learning is enhanced by positivity. When teachers help their students feel motivated and excited, they learn better. (By the way, the same goes for self-studying English - it helps to be positive!)

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1. **All the Rage** - juda zamonaviy, olifta

Yoga pants are **all the rage** in North America right now, but in two years probably nobody will be wearing them.

2. **Meeting of the Minds** – juda katta kelishuvga erishmoq

At first the negotiations weren't going well, but when the president of the company and I sat down over drinks, we had a real **meeting of the minds**.

3. **Scare the Living Daylights out of Someone** - Biror kishini qattiq qo'rqitish

I know my boyfriend was just trying to be nice, but when I opened the door to my apartment and everyone yelled “Surprise!” it **scared the living daylights** out of me.

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7. **Out of Sight, Out of Mind**- Agar biror narsani yoki kimnidir ko'rmasangiz, u narsa yoki odam haqida unutishga moyil bo'lasiz.

When I broke up with Jake, I was heartbroken. But since he moved away, I hardly ever think about him. **Out of sight, out of mind!**

8. **Tear-Jerker** - Sizni yig'lab yuboradigan film yoki kitob

The film “Love Story,” with its story of young love cut short by death, was one of the most successful **tear-jerkers** of all time.

9. **Pet Peeve** - Sizni ayniqsa bezovta qiladigan kichik narsa

My **pet peeve** is people who bring large numbers of items to the express checkout at the supermarket.

10. **Pull Yourself Together** - O'z his-tuyg'ularingizni boshqaring; kuchli hissiy xafagarchilikdan xalos bo'lish.

I know it was hard seeing your ex-boyfriend at the bar, but you need to **pull yourself together** so we can go home.

11. **Get Carried Away**- Haddan tashqari ishtiyoqli bo'ling

Sure, you can invest a little money, but don't **get carried away** – people lose lots of money on the stock market.

12. **Think Big** - Katta rejalarni ko'rib chiqing; tafsilotlar bilan ortiqcha tashvishlanishdan saqlaning

Sales this year have been good. Caitlin said we should **think big** and consider whole new product lines.

13. **Not Playing with a Full Deck** - Ahmoq, aqliy zaif yoki zaif

John's suggestions in the meeting were ridiculous. Sometimes I think he's **not playing with a full deck**.

14. **Under the Impression** - Biror narsaga ishonish, ehtimol noto'g'ri

I was **under the impression** that you were going to pick me up at the airport.

15. **Out of Sorts** - Bir oz kasal; o'zini yaxshi his qilmayapti

Sorry I was so quiet during the meeting. I've been **out of sorts** all day.

16. **Short Fuse** - Tez jahl; tez g'azablanish tendentsiyasi

Brandon has a **short fuse**, but he calms down as quickly as he gets angry.

17. **Off One's Rocker** - Aqldan ozgan, aqldan ozgan, aqldan ozgan

Have you heard Dmitri is going to try to climb Mt. Rinjani in the rainy season? He must be **off his rocker**.

18. **Bang One’s Head Against the Wall (Against a Brick Wall) -**

Harakat qilmasdan biror narsa qilishga qayta-qayta harakat qiling

Susana has been working on the data for three hours, but she says she’s just **banging her head against the wall**.

19. **Young at Heart -** Yoshdan qat'i nazar, yoshlik dunyoqarashiga ega

bo'lish

Jack is **young at heart**. He’s 84 years old, but he’s always willing to go out dancing.

20.Thanks for your help. - Har qanday narsa uchun rahmat aytish odamlarni qadrlashini, kerakli va sevishini his qiladi. Siz quyidagi tuzilmalardan birini qo'llashingiz mumkin:

Thanks for the lovely birthday card you sent in the mail. It really made my birthday special!

20. **I couldn’t have done it without you.-** Bu ibora kimgadir o'zining

almashtirib bo'lmaydiganligini bilish imkonini beradi.

Thanks for helping me plan this wedding. I couldn’t have done it without you!

22. **I’m so proud of you.** - Boshqa birov bilan faxrlanish insonlar uchun eng baxtli tuyg'ulardan biridir. Shunday ekan, birovning qilgan ishidan mamnun bo'lsangiz, ular bilan faxrlanishingizni ayting.

Your art portfolio is fantastic—you’ve worked really hard! I’m so proud of you.

23. **You’re so awesome.** - Bu ibora juda oddiy, ammo samarali.

You’re so talented. You play the piano really well!

24. **I appreciate your support.** - "Men sizni qadrlayman" kimgadir siz ularni qadrlashingizni aytadi. Agar kimdir sizga yordam bersa, demak u sizga yordam beradi yoki siz bilan rozi bo'ladi.

I appreciate your positive attitude.

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